

COMPARATIVE INVESTIGATION OF REPRODUCTIVE PERFORMANCE OF TWO EDIBLE ECOTYPE OF GIANT LAND SNAILS FED BANANA LEAVES IN THE HUMID TROPICAL ZONE OF CROSS RIVER STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the reproductive potentials of two edible ecotype of giant land snails (*Archachatina marginata ovum* and *Archachatina marginata Saturalis*) fed banana leaves in the humid tropical zone of Cross River State within a 16 week period. The reproductive potentials of the two ecotypes of giant lands snail revealed that *Archachatina marginata ovum* performed better ($P < 0.05$) than *Archachatina marginata Saturalis* in terms of total number of eggs laid, clutch size, incubation period, egg weight, egg length and egg width. However, no differences ($P > 0.05$) was observed between the two ecotypes on their Percent egg hatchability.

KEY WORDS: Reproductive Performance, Ecotype, Giant Land Snail

INTRODUCTION

Edible African giant land snail is small animal commonly classified as mini-livestock and is widely distributed all over the humid tropical zones of Africa (Ibom *et al*, 2008). This snail species according to Ogogo (2004) is native to Nigeria but has spread to other African countries and beyond. Captivity is attracting the keen interest of both scientist and farmers suggesting the potentials of their subspecies as snails for commercial farming in humid tropics (Ubua *et al*. 2012). The population explosion implies that many people require the supply of protein in their diet because it's important role in human well being which include growth, maintenance of hormonal and enzymatic activities and improvement of the defence mechanism of the body (Ademolu *et al* 2004). The survival, growth, development and reproduction of snail like that of other animal species depend highly on the quality of feed consumed. Thompson and Cheney [2004] identified various factors that can greatly influence the survival and growth of snails. These factors include husbandry, population density, stress, temperature, feed and breeding technology used. Murphy [2001] also listed humidity, temperature and light as environmental factors critical to the activity, behavior and reproduction of snails. Information on two snail's ecotype in view of the reproductive performance in the humid tropical zone for commercial snail farmers is scanty. The experiments was aimed at comparing the investigation carried out on the reproductive performance of the two ecotypes of giant land snail fed banana leaves in in humid tropical zone of Cross River State.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in the Snailery unit of the Animal Science Department, University of Calabar, Cross River. Snails, snail cages, banana leaves were the experimental materials used in this study. Dimensions of the cages constructed with wood and wire gauze were 45cm (length) 45cm (width) x40cm (height) loamy soil was collected, loosened and sterilized to kill all Organisms (nematode). Sterilization of soil was done by heating the soil. Loamy soil was preferred because snails show preference for neutral to slightly alkaline pH soils. The forage of choice for this study was fresh banana leaves because snails show preference for this feed (Ubua *et al*., 2012). The two ecotypes of giant and snails for data collection were adult *Archachatina marginata ovum* and *Archachatina marginata Saturalis*. A total of sixty (60) sexually matured snails were used in this study with thirty (30) snails each of *Archachatina marginata ovum* and *Archachatina marginata saturalis*. Fifteen (15) snails from each species of the snails were allotted to the treatment diet which was replicated 3 times with 5 snails per replicate. The snails were fed with banana leaves. Data on reproductive parameters were collected on weekly basis for a period of 16 weeks. Data collected included total number of eggs laid, clutch size, incubation

period, percent egg hatchability, egg weight, egg length, egg width. T-Test was used to analyze the reproductive parameters of the two ectotypes and the means separated using Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of reproductive performance of the two ectotype of snails are shown in Table 1. The results showed that *Archachatina marginata ovum* are more prolific and laid more eggs (54) than *Archachatina marginata saturalis* (36). The findings were similar to reports of Ibom *et al.* (2008) on black stained *Archachatina marginata ovum*. These observations on prolificacy may be due to inherent genetic potential of the snails. Ubu (2011) observed that eggs laid by *Archachatina marginata ovum* are more and relatively larger in size than those laid by *Archachatina marginata saturalis* probably because of size of breed. The number of eggs laid per clutch by *Archachatina marginata ovum* fed banana leaves were significantly ($P < 0.05$) different from *Archachatina marginata saturalis*. Clutch sizes of *Archachatina marginata ovum* observed in this study are larger than those of *Archachatina marginata saturalis*. This may be as a result of their genetic make up, breed of snail as well as haemolymph characteristics. This conforms with Ibom *et al.* (2008) that there is variation in reproductive activities between subspecies of a particular breed. However, *Archachatina marginata ovum* recorded high clutch size (Table 1). Okon *et al.* (2009) reported that age and environment can influence egg and clutch size of snail. The mean clutch size of *Archachatina marginata ovum* in this study (Table 1) is lower than reports by Reid (1989) and Omole and Kehinde (2005). Okon *et al.* (2010) recorded high clutch sizes in albino snails for the same subspecies than that in this study. The mean clutch size of *Archachatina marginata saturalis* (Table 1) is lower than reports of Payne and Wilson (1999) and Ejidike *et al.* (2002). The mean incubation period of this study indicated that *Archachatina marginata ovum* had the longest incubation period of 30.42 days which was significantly ($P < 0.05$) different from that of *Archachatina marginata saturalis* (26.52 days). Difference in incubation periods could be due to differences in genetic composition, environment, breed and soil condition such as relative humidity, temperature and soil composition. The values obtained in this study indicated that incubation period of *Archachatina marginata ovum* (Table 1) is higher than the values reported by Mfon (1986) and Ubu *et al.* (2012). Ibom *et al.* (2008) reported incubation period from 14 to 28 days for *Archachatina marginata ovum* which are lower than the mean value obtained in this study (Table 1). The mean incubation period obtained for *Archachatina marginata saturalis* in this study is higher than the reports of Ewa (2007). The results in Table 1 indicated that mean percent egg hatchability of *Archachatina marginata ovum* is 70.89% while *Archachatina marginata saturalis* had 69.51%. These values showed no significant ($P > 0.05$) differences between percent egg hatchability of both subspecies fed banana leaves. However, mean percent egg hatchability (Table 1) of both subspecies is higher than 66.90% and 68.40% reported by Awesu (1980) and Ogogo (1989), respectively. The results in Table 1 indicated that mean egg weight of *Archachatina marginata ovum* is 1.70g while *Archachatina marginata saturalis* had 1.55. Values of egg weight in both subspecies were significantly ($P < 0.05$) different on banana leaves. Disparity could be that as hatching days keep decreasing during incubation, the egg weight also decreases. The decrease in egg weight may be caused by environmental conditions. This observation is similar to the reports of Ibom *et al.* (2008) that a decrease in egg weight is attributed to exposure to relative humidity and temperature as well as soil condition which differs from the near constant maternal (uterine) environment which they belong before lay. Mean egg weight of *Archachatina marginata ovum* in this study is larger than values reported by Ibom *et al.* (2008) and Okon *et al.* (2009) in white-skinned ectotype of the same subspecies. In contrast, Ogogo (2004) obtained higher values in *Archachatina marginata saturalis*. Results in Table 1 showed that mean egg length of *Archachatina marginata saturalis* had 12.87mm these values showed significant ($P < 0.05$) differences between egg length of both subspecies on banana leaves. Differences in egg length between these subspecies could be a result of breed differences soil texture, genetic make up. Mean egg length (Table 1) of *Archachatina marginata ovum* is higher than 14.8mm and 14.3mm reported by Ibom *et al.* (2008) and Okon *et al.* (2010), respectively. Mean egg length of *Archachatina marginata saturalis* in this study is lower than the value reported by Amubode (1994). Results in Table 1 indicated that mean egg width of *Archachatina marginata ovum* is 12.28mm while *Archachatina marginata saturalis* had 10.87mm. Values showed significant ($P < 0.05$) difference between egg width of both subspecies fed banana leaves. Variation in egg width may be due to age and size of the snails, incubation condition such as water uptake. Values of egg width obtained in this study for both subspecies are higher than 10.78mm and 16mm reported by Okon *et al.* (2010) and Awesu (1980) respectively.

CONCLUSION

The result of this study investigated and examined the reproductive potentials of *Archachatina marginata ovum* and observed that this subspecies can perform better than *Archachatina marginata saturalis* when fed banana leaves

Table 1 Reproductive investigation of adult *Archachatina marginata ovum* and *Archachatina marginata saturalis* fed banana leaves for 16 weeks

PARAMETER	<i>Archachatina marginata ovum</i>	<i>Archachatina marginata saturalis</i>	SEM
Total number of eggs laid	54	36	
Mean clutch size	6.14 ^a	4.50 ^b	0.59
Mean incubation period (days)	30.42 ^a	26.52 ^b	0.19
Mean percent egg hatchability (%)	70.89	69.51	0.08
Mean egg weight (g)	1.70 ^a	1.55 ^b	0.01
Mean egg length (mm)	15.12 ^a	12.87 ^b	0.36
Mean egg width (mm)	12.28 ^a	10.87 ^b	0.20

SEM = Standard error of mean

^{ab} Mean values with different superscript in the same row are significantly (P<0.05) different

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